

INFLUENCE OF COMPATIBILIZER AMOUNT ON ADHESION AND PROPERTIES OF PE-BASED BIOCOMPOSITES

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Original scientific paper
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5255462
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Abstract: *Due to low density, high stiffness, moderate strength and low price, biocomposites with polyethylene (PE) as matrix and biomass as reinforcement are also gaining the attention of researchers in the field of packaging. The interfacial bonding between the nonpolar PE matrix and the polar biomass determines the properties of the biocomposites. The interfacial bonding can be improved by surface treatment of the biomass or by the addition of a suitable compatibilizer. The compatibilizer, in the present case maleic anhydride grafted onto the PE main chain, can also facilitate the dispersion of the biomass in the PE matrix. In addition, the nature of the compatibilizer can also be used to increase the surface tension of the biocomposite. This triple compatibilization function was tested with the PE-HD matrix and the addition of 2 wt.%, 3 wt.%, 4 wt.%, and 5 wt.% PE -g- MA compatibilizer. Either 30 wt.% waste paper or miscanthus fibers were used as reinforcement. Adhesion was tested using IML technology during injection molding. The mechanical and thermal properties of the biocomposites were determined using bending and tensile tests, DMA, DSC, TGA and impact tests. An improvement in adhesion was obtained with increasing amount of compatibilizer. Stiffness decreased with increasing amount of compatibilizer while strength increased. Impact strength was increased with the amount of compatibilizer. The results indicate that the compatibilizer can successfully replace the surface treatment of biomass while promoting adhesion on the surface without additional surface treatment such as corona treatment. The results are promising for the use of this approach for*

the formulation of biocomposites for the packaging sector, as two additional steps are avoided, thus reducing the price of the final product.

Keywords: PE, compatibilizer, adhesion, biocomposites

1 INTRODUCTION

In the packaging field, terms rigid plastics includes bottles, jars, tubs, buckets and pails. The development of processing technologies for the production of rigid plastic packaging has contributed to the growth of this segment. One of the crucial aspects is the decoration of this product. A very commonly used technology for manufacturing rigid packaging is injection molding (Hannay et al., 2002). The main advantage of plastic packaging is the low density of plastics (Susan & John, 2016). In order to maintain the low weight of the packaging, the decoration technology of the packaging attracts the interest of the researchers. The market dictates the different decoration effects. The distinction needs to be made on the packaging containers as well as on the design and type of labeling. Decorative effects are three dimensional, color effects, contrasts, gloss and matte effects, metallic or reflective effects and many others. This can be achieved with films, foils, labels, inks, paints, and coatings. Some of these technologies require additional processing steps, some have a large environmental impact, and some can be integrated into existing production lines with minor modifications. (Crutchley, 2014). An interesting technology for applying labels to packaging containers is in-mold labeling (IML). This technology for decoration offers many possibilities to achieve the best possible quality for visual impact and minimize double handling, as would be the case with printing. With IML technology, very thin label material can be used. The position of the label in the mold is maintained by either a vacuum or an electrostatic charge. Most robotic label placement systems currently available do not require a special injection molding machine and can be easily connected to most modern injection molding machines with quick clamping systems. As a process for high quality decoration of injection molded packaging, IML has proven to be viable and demand continues to increase as graphic requirements become more demanding (Chen et al., 2010; Crutchley, 2014; Hannay et al., 2002). Labels for IML must have good adhesion to the surface of the injection molded plastic part. The best results can be achieved when the injected melt partially bonds with the film, improving the adhesion between the film and the molded part (Chen et al., 2010; Crutchley, 2014). In a multilayer structure, as in the case of IML, the adhesion between layers is difficult to realize, especially with the different polarities of the layers. To ensure better adhesion, two main approaches can be used, namely surface

pretreatment and material modification. Maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene (PE -g- MA) is most commonly used for the reactive compounding of polyethylene. PE -g- MA enhances the surface interaction between PE and other polar polymers and added fibers (Barczewski et al., 2018; Gao et al., 2012; Garcia-Garcia et al., 2016; Husseinsyah et al., 2013; Nugent, 2005; Petchwattana et al., 2012; Rahman et al., 2016; Roumeli et al., 2015). In the present work, PE -g- MA was used as a compatibilizer for biomass in PE -HD matrix, as a surfactant for biomass and as an adhesion promoter for IML technology.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Sample

Commercially available PE -HD with the trade name SABIC HDPE CC2056 was purchased from Sabic, Saudi Arabia. Commercially available PLA with the trade name Ingeo 7001D was purchased from Resinex, Slovenia. Commercially available miscanthus fibers were donated by the company Krilotim, Slovenia. Waste paper (waste from paper production) was donated by the company Papirnica Vevče, Slovenia. A commercially available PE -g- MA compatibilizer with the trade name Exxelor PE 1040 was purchased from the company ExxonMobil, Belgium. Commercially available lubricant with the trade name Crodamide EBS-MB-(GD) was purchased from Croda, Italy. Commercially available antioxidant with the trade name AT 10 was purchased from Amik Italia, Italy. The composition of the samples is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of the samples (M-miscanthus fibers, WP-waste paper, C-compatibilizer, L-lubricant, AO-antioxidant)

Sample	PE-HD (wt.%)	PLA (wt.%)	M (wt.%)	WP (wt.%)	C (wt.%)	L (wt.%)	AO (wt.%)
15_02	66.62		30		2	1	0.38
15_03	64.62		30		4	1	0.38
15_04	62.62		30		6	1	0.38
60_01	66.62			30	2	1	0.38
60_02	64.62			30	4	1	0.38
60_03	65.62			30	3	1	0.38
60_04	63.62			30	5	1	0.38
63_01	65.62		30		3	1	0.38
63_02	64.62		30		4	1	0.38
63_03	63.62		30		5	1	0.38
63_04	65.62			30	3	1	0.38
63_05	64.62			30	4	1	0.38
63_06	63.62			30	5	1	0.38

2. 2 Processing

For the compounding cycle, the materials were mixed separately and extruded on the Labtech LTE 20-44 twin screw extruder. The screws had a diameter of 20 mm, an L/D ratio of 44:1, a screw speed of 300 rpm, and an increasing temperature profile from the hopper (135 °C) to the die (160 °C). After compounding, the two produced filaments were cooled in a water bath and cut into pellets with a length of about 5 mm and a diameter of 3 mm.

Injection molding was performed on Krauss Maffei 50-180 CX with a screw diameter of 30 mm. The temperature profile was increasing from the hopper (145 °C) to the nozzle (160 °C). The mold temperature was set to 45 °C and the cooling time to 9 s. The back pressure was set to 195 bar and the screw speed to 175 rpm. The injection speed was set to 50 mm/s and 10 mm/s for the last 2 mm.

2. 3 Characterization

Flexural and tensile tests were carried out on Shimadzu AG -X plus according to ISO 178 and ISO 527-1 respectively. Five measurements were taken for each specimen. In tensile tests, tensile stiffness (E_t), tensile strength (σ_m), tensile yield strain (ϵ_m), and strain at break (ϵ_{tb}) were determined. In bending, the flexural stiffness (E_f), flexural strength (σ_{fM}) and yield strain (ϵ_{fM}) were evaluated. Thermomechanical properties were investigated using a Perkin Elmer DMA 8000. The specimens were heated at 2 °C/min from 25 °C to 140 °C under air atmosphere. A frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 20 μ m in dual cantilever mode were used. Thermal measurements were performed using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC 2, Mettler Toledo) under nitrogen atmosphere (20 mL/min). The temperature of the samples was raised from -40 to 180 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min and held in the molten state for 5 min to erase their thermal history. After cooling at 10 °C/min, the samples were reheated to 180 °C at 10 °C/min. The crystallization temperature (T_c), crystallization enthalpy (ΔH_c), melting temperature (T_m), and melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) were determined from the cooling and the second heating scan. Thermogravimetric analyzes (TGA) were performed using a Perkin Elmer TGA 4000 thermal analyzer. Analyzes were performed in a nitrogen atmosphere (20 mL/min) from 40 to 550 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min, followed by an isothermal segment in an oxygen atmosphere (20 mL/min) at 550 °C for 5 min using an Al₂O₃ crucible without a lid. Impact tests were performed using a pendulum Dongguan Liyi Test Equipment, type LY -XJJD5, according to ISO 179. The distance between the supports was 60 mm, and a pendulum with 5 J and 2 J was used for the impact and notched impact tests, respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties

As expected, the addition of miscanthus to the PE -HD matrix along with compatibilizer and additives (Table 2, Figure 1) increased strength and stiffness to a greater extent than the addition of waste paper. With increasing amount of compatibilizer, the stiffness of the composites is not affected while the strength is increased with more than 4 wt.% as well as the strain at break. The compatibilizer improved the interfacial bonding between miscanthus or waste paper and the PE-HD matrix, but for the 30 wt.% biomass addition, the required amount of compatibilizer is at least 4 wt.% to allow good wetting of the entire surface of the biomass. Maleic anhydride is chemically bound to the biomass surface during compounding due to its high shear content. Good interactions between the compatibilizer and the biomass surface additionally enable better dispersion of the biomass particles in the PE-HD matrix. A higher amount of compatibilizer allows even better bonding of the biomass in the PE-HD matrix, resulting in higher strain at break and higher strength of the biocomposites. Higher stiffness, higher strength and higher strain at break are good indicators of excellent compatibilization of the biomass in the PE -HD matrix, even though the surface of the biomass was not pretreated before compounding. With the proper processing parameters, sufficient shear could be generated during compounding and injection molding to allow the compatibilizer to wet the biomass surface and open the maleic anhydride rings, which could then be chemically bonded to the biomass surface.

Table 2: Summarized results from the bending and tensile tests with standard deviation values

Sample	Bending test results			Tensile test results			
	E_f (GPa)	σ_{fM} (MPa)	ϵ_{fM} (%)	E_t (GPa)	σ_m (MPa)	ϵ_m (%)	ϵ_{tb} (%)
15_02	2.15±0.03	39.0±0.3	5.6±0.1	2.38±0.13	33.5±0.2	3.0±0.1	3.1±0.1
15_03	2.16±0.02	40.5±0.1	6.0±0.1	2.64±0.15	36.4±0.2	3.5±0.1	3.6±0.2
15_04	2.05±0.02	38.9±0.1	6.0±0.1	2.44±0.09	35.3±1.5	3.9±0.2	4.2±0.3
60_01	1.59±0.03	30.7±0.1	6.8±0.1	1.98±0.13	32.2±0.5	5.4±0.4	5.5±0.5
60_02	1.60±0.04	31.6±0.1	6.8±0.1	1.63±0.09	32.6±0.2	6.4±0.1	6.9±0.4
60_03	1.57±0.01	30.8±0.1	6.8±0.1	1.67±0.12	31.0±0.5	6.3±0.2	6.7±0.4
60_04	1.49±0.07	30.6±0.2	6.9±0.1	1.68±0.09	32.3±0.4	6.5±0.4	6.7±0.6
63_01	1.74±0.02	33.7±0.3	6.1±0.1	2.14±0.24	29.6±1.1	4.8±0.5	5.2±0.5
63_02	1.77±0.02	34.2±0.2	6.1±0.1	1.82±0.20	29.4±0.3	5.0±0.6	5.3±0.6
63_03	1.79±0.02	35.0±0.2	6.2±0.1	1.97±0.19	30.7±0.3	5.6±0.7	6.1±0.8
63_04	1.48±0.01	30.0±0.1	6.9±0.1	2.00±0.19	31.7±0.4	7.1±0.2	7.8±0.3
63_05	1.44±0.01	29.7±0.1	6.9±0.1	1.91±0.35	31.4±0.5	7.2±0.5	8.2±0.6
63_06	1.53±0.01	31.0±0.2	6.9±0.1	1.81±0.23	34.2±0.5	7.0±0.1	7.6±0.5

Figure 1: Summarized results of the tensile strength (bars) and strain at break (line)

3. 2 Thermo-mechanical properties

The storage modulus curves (Figures 2-4) show a similar dependence of storage modulus on temperature. A significant decrease in storage modulus is observed at the onset of melting of the PE-HD matrix. The amount of compatibilizer has no significant effect on the storage modulus of the composites. For the composites with miscanthus, the storage modulus is higher than the storage modulus for composites with waste paper, which is in good correlation with flexural and tensile tests. The only exception is sample 63_02, where the storage modulus is lower from room temperature up to 70 °C, above 70 °C the storage modulus increases to the values of the other composites with miscanthus. The reason for this behavior could be due to the higher particle size of miscanthus, where the reinforcing effect of the fibers is more pronounced at higher temperatures. From the results, it can be concluded that the deviation in biomass properties has a greater effect on the storage modulus than the amount of compatibilizer added in the composites. The loss modulus can be related to the internal friction in the biocomposites. The peak of loss modulus curve can be related to the α -transition of the rigid amorphous segments in the PE-HD crystals (Mohanty et al., 2006) and is related to the reorientation of the defects in the PE -HD crystals. For all samples, the peak of loss modulus was shifted to higher temperatures with increasing amount of compatibilizer, which can be attributed to the decrease of matrix mobility at relaxation temperature caused by better interfacial

adhesion between biomass and matrix. We can conclude that the addition of the compatibilizer facilitates the dispersion of the biomass (both miscanthus and waste paper) in the PE-HD matrix and improves the surface adhesion and toughness.

Figure 2: Summarized results of storage modulus for the samples 15_02 to 15_04

Figure 3: Summarized results of storage modulus for the samples 60_01 to 60_04

Figure 4: Summarized results of storage modulus for the samples 63_01 to 63_06

Figure 5: Summarized results of loss modulus for the samples 15_02 to 15_04

Figure 6: Summarized results of loss modulus for the samples 60_01 to 60_04

Figure 7: Summarized results of loss modulus for the samples 63_01 to 63_06

3. 3 Thermal properties

With increasing amount of compatibilizer, the degree of crystallization was higher for the biocomposites with waste paper addition, the bimodal behavior

was observed with the addition of miscanthus, with the maximum values at 2 wt.% and 6 wt.% addition of miscanthus and with the lower values in the range of 3 wt.% to 5 wt.%. Already at DMA, the influence of miscanthus particle sizes was most likely the reason for different behavior. Also, crystallization can be inhibited by the addition of larger particles, with the steric barrier preventing crystallization of the PE-HD matrix. The melting and crystallization temperatures are not affected.

Table 3: Summarized results from the 2nd heating from DSC tests

<i>Sample</i>	<i>T_m</i> (°C)	<i>ΔH_m</i> (J/g)	<i>T_c</i> (°C)	<i>ΔH_c</i> (J/g)	<i>X_c</i> (%)
15_02	131.1	132.4	116.5	132.1	67.8
15_03	132.1	115.9	116.6	111.2	61.2
15_04	131.6	122.2	115.9	113.6	66.6
60_01	130.9	140.4	116.9	134.5	71.9
60_02	131.0	125.9	116.9	113.9	66.5
60_03	131.2	133.0	116.7	126.9	69.2
60_04	132.2	136.1	115.9	132.8	73.0
63_01	130.2	126.4	117.1	120.7	65.7
63_02	134.4	104.3	113.6	98.9	55.1
63_03	132.4	109.1	115.0	107.8	58.5
63_04	134.9	111.5	114.3	110.0	58.0
63_05	132.3	122.7	115.9	118.0	64.8
63_06	132.1	124.4	116.3	121.9	66.7

3. 4 Impact properties

Higher impact strength values were measured for the biocomposites with waste paper than for the biocomposites with miscanthus. On the other hand, higher notched impact strength values were measured for the samples with miscanthus. As the amount of compatibilizer increased, the impact strength and notched impact strength values increased. It can be concluded that the compatibilizer favours the interfacial adhesion between the biomass and the PE-HD matrix, and the surface area of the biomass coated with the compatibilizer increases with increasing amount of the compatibilizer. Waste paper in the PE-HD matrix improved the impact strength to a greater extent than miscanthus, where the smaller diameter of the particles to a bigger extent compared to miscanthus where the particle size is bigger. The influence of the mineral filler in the waste paper resulted in a decrease in the notched impact strength of the composites compared to the composites with miscanthus due to the easier propagation of cracks in the biocomposites filled with the mineral filler with aspect ratio close to 1.

Figure 8: Summarized results of toughness: impact strength (bars) and notched impact strength (line)

3. 5 In-mould labeling

Several different materials were used conducting in-mold labeling with the composites. The best adhesion was achieved with the composites with 5 wt.% and 6 wt.% addition of the compatibilizer to the PE-HD matrix. Printed films, printed textile labels and NFC chips were tested. The best adhesion was achieved with the printed textile labels and with sample 15_04. The tests showed that the addition of the compatibilizer in an amount exceeding the compatibilization of the biomass can contribute to the adhesion of the labels and the biocomposites without the need for surface treatment, as in the case of the separate step of labeling after the production of injection molded parts.

4 CONCLUSION

The research work focused on the amount of added compatibilizer in biocomposites with PE-HD matrix and biomass on the adhesion of labels in in-mold technology and the influence on the properties of the injection molded parts. The increasing amount of compatibilizer does not drastically affect the stiffness, but increases the strength and elongation at break. The good interfacial adhesion between biomass and PE-HD matrix was further confirmed by the shift of loss modulus to higher temperatures and the increasing impact and notched impact strength with increasing amount of compatibilizer in the

biocomposites. The particle size of the biomass had the greatest influence on the behavior of the composites. Higher particle sizes decreased stiffness, storage modulus, impact strength and crystallinity. A higher improvement in mechanical properties was obtained with miscanthus compared to waste paper, probably due to the high content of inorganic filler in the waste paper, which also caused a decrease in notched impact strength. Label adhesion was best when at least 5 wt% of the compatibilizer was added and was not affected by the added biomass. We have shown that the one-step labeling process is feasible with the right amount of added compatibilizer in the biocomposites and can also be used for packaging applications, since additional production steps such as cleaning and activation of the surface before labeling can be avoided resulting in savings of time and expenses.

The correlation between the amount of added compatibilizer and the choice of material for the labels should be investigated in further research.

Acknowledgments: *The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support received from the Slovenian Smart Specialization Program (CEL.CYCLE - <http://celkrog.si/?lang=en>, grant number C3330-16-529004).*

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